

Research Article

The Positive Effect of Skd Plus Iot and Hbo2t In The Treatment Of Cancer [Introducing Soroush Cancer Treatment Protocol (Sctp)]

Somayeh Zaminpira¹, Soroush Niknamian^{2*}, Stephanie Seneff³ and Dominic D'Agostino⁴

¹Liberty University (LU), Military Medicine, United States

²Cellular & Molecular Biology, Weston A Price Foundation, Washington, United States

³Senior Research Scientist, Massachusetts Institute of Technology Computer Science & Artificial Intelligence Lab, Boston, United States

⁴Associate Professor, Molecular Pharmacology and Physiology, University of South Florida Morsani College of Medicine, University of South Florida, United States

*Corresponding author: Soroush Niknamian, Cellular & Molecular Biology, Weston A Price Foundation, Washington, USA; Email: so.niknamian@gmail.com

Received: March 12, 2019; Accepted: March 21, 2019; Published: March 25, 2019;

Abstract

Background: The aim of this research is to figure out the effectiveness of the Soroush Cancer Treatment Protocol (SCTP) which is based on the Evolutionary Metabolic Hypothesis of Cancer (EMHC) and introducing the Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD) plus Intravenous Ozone Therapy (IOT) in Phase (1) on 54 cancer patients, and combination of Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy with vitamin/mineral and herbal supplementation beside the SKD and IOT in Phase (2) of this research on the remaining 31 cancer patients.

Introduction: Cancer based on the introduction of EMHC by Dr. Somayeh Zaminpira and Dr. Soroush Niknamian in 2017, is an evolutionary metabolic disease and through the incline of the Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) and the Butterfly Effect in normal eukaryotic cells, the mitochondria become damaged or shut down. Cancer cells are primitive eukaryotic cells which have existed since around 1.5 billion years ago before the entrance of mitochondrion as endosymbiont.

Materials and Methods: Based on the researches from 1928–2016 and the experimentation of cancer treatments and protocols on cancer patients, we have reached a treatment and decided to test it on 54 voluntary cancer patients in the first stage of their disease. In this treatment we used a 5-day water fasting state, the Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD) designed by ourselves and Intravenous Ozone Therapy (IOT) in the duration of 90 days (Phase 1) and another 90 days (Phase 2) with the entrance of Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBO2T) and several supplements which have been effective in previous studies on cancer patients. We have used the measurement of saliva PH, the MRI device and statistical methods to test the shrinkage of the tumors.

Results: After Phase (1) of this research on 54 patients the average percentage decrease in the tumors was 58% and after Phase (2) on 31 remaining cancer patients the average percentage decrease in the tumors was 98.8%. The average saliva PH in the fasting state of the cancer patients improved from acidic to alkaline as well.

Conclusion: in conclusion, we have reached an effective cancer treatment based on SCTP by the usage of SKD, IOT, HBO2T and several supplements. There was an obvious improvement of cancer tumor decrease, lifestyle, saliva PH and we did not observe any side effects or cachexia in any of the patients.

Keywords: EMHC Hypothesis, SKD, IOT, ROS, HBO2T, SCTP

Introduction

Evolutionary Metabolic Hypothesis of Cancer (EMHC)

The first living cells on Earth are thought to have arisen more than 3.5×10^9 years ago, when the Earth was not more than about 109 years old. The environment lacked oxygen but was presumably rich in geochemically produced organic molecules, and some of the earliest metabolic pathways for producing ATP may have resembled present-day forms of fermentation. In the process of fermentation, ATP is made by a phosphorylation event that harnesses the energy released

when a hydrogen-rich organic molecule, such as glucose, is partly oxidized. The electrons lost from the oxidized organic molecules are transferred via NADH or NADPH to a different organic molecule or to a different part of the same molecule, which thereby becomes more reduced. At the end of the fermentation process, one or more of the organic molecules produced are excreted into the medium as metabolic waste products. Others, such as pyruvate, are retained by the cell for biosynthesis. The excreted end-products are different in different organisms, but they tend to be organic acids. Among the most important of such products in bacterial cells are lactic acid which also accumulates in anaerobic mammalian glycolysis, and formic, acetic,

propionic, butyric, and succinic acids [1]. The first cell on the earth before the entrance of the bacteria did contain a nucleus and used the fermentation process to produce ATP for its energy. Then an aerobic proteo-bacterium enters the eukaryote either as a prey or a parasite and manages to avoid digestion. It then became an endosymbiont. As we observe, the fermentation process used the glucose or even glutamine to produce ATP, but the aerobic process used the glucose, fat and protein to produce more ATP than the previous one. The symbio-genesis of the mitochondria is based on the natural selection of Charles Darwin. Based on Otto Warburg Hypothesis, in nearly all cancer cells, the mitochondrion is shut down or is defective and the cancer cell does not use its mitochondria to produce ATP [2]. This process of adaptation is based on Lamarckian Hypothesis of Evolution and the normal cells goes back to the most primitive time of evolution to protect itself from apoptosis and uses the fermentation process like the first living cells 1.5 billion years ago. Therefore, cancer is an evolutionary metabolic disease which uses glucose as the main food to produce ATP and Lactic Acid. The prime cause of cancer is the abundance of Reactive Oxygen Species produced by mitochondria that is a threat to the living normal cell and causes mitochondrial damage mainly in its cristae [3].

Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD)

Ketogenic diet is a kind of regime which uses high fat content and low carbohydrate. This diet changes the metabolic state into the condition called Ketosis. After several days, fat becomes your body's primary energy source which causes an increase in the levels of compounds which are called "ketones" in the blood [4]. In general, a ketogenic diet used for weight loss is about 60–75% of calories as fat, with 15–30% of calories from protein and 5–10% of calories from carbs. However, when a ketogenic diet is being used therapeutically for the treatment of cancer, the fat content may be significantly higher that is up to 90% of calories, and the protein content lower [5]. The SKD contains 80% saturated fat, 15% protein with the lowest Glutamine content and 5% high-fiber carbohydrates mainly in the form of cruciferous vegetables.

Materials and Methods

Based on the researches from 1928–2016 and the experimentation of cancer treatments and protocols on cancer patients, we have reached a treatment and decided to test it on 54 voluntaries cancer patients. In this treatment we used a 5-day water fasting state to put the cancer patients body on cannibalism state. In this period of the experiment, normal body cells digest abnormal cancerous cells for food. Thomas N. Seyfried et al, 2012 After the water fasting period, we began the Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD) designed by ourselves and Intravenous Ozone Therapy (IOT) in the duration of 90 days (Phase 1) and another 90 days (Phase 2) with the entrance of Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBO2T) and several supplements which have been effective in previous studies on cancer patients. We have also used the measurement of the saliva pH in the fasting state, the MRI device and statistical methods to test the decrease in size of the tumors. The dosage of the intravenous ozone therapy (IOT) which we used was: 42ug/cc on the first month, 56 ug/cc on the second month and 70ug/cc on the third month in the Phase

(1) and 70ug/cc once per week and HBO2T twice per week in the Phase (2) of our research. This type of IOT was due to a decrease in the allergic reaction by the patients. Entering the vitamin/mineral, herbal supplements and probiotic foods benefited cancer patients in their mood and decreased the possibilities of depression and anxiety.

PHASE (1)

In Phase (1) of our research, there were two sessions of IOT on Saturdays and Tuesdays. There was no supplementation in this Phase of our experiment. The SKD is a type of Ketogenic Diet which consists of 80% saturated fat (Organic Cow Butter, Organic Cow Tallow and Coconut oil), 15% protein with lowest Glutamine content (Fish meat, shrimp, organic calf meat, organic whole eggs, organic chicken and low glutamine protein powder.) and 5% complex-high fiber carbohydrate (whole vegetables, cruciferous vegetables, lettuce, white mushrooms and dark green fruits). The consumption of any dairy, artificial sweeteners as well as stevia, vegetable oils, margarines, pig's meat, soy products, sugar, alcohol, gluten and fruit juices were prohibited in this research. The Total calorie intake of this Diet should be 1200–1500 Cal/Day. The patients used fermented foods (Kimchee, Miso or Natto) every day for their benefits as probiotics to improve their digestion and absorbing important vitamins/minerals. For the improvement of the patients' body pH and absorbing some important minerals, they have been given vegetable juice twice per day (500 ml/day). The intravenous ozone therapy (IOT) which we used was: 42ug/cc on the first month, 56 ug/cc on the second month and 70ug/cc on the third month. This type of IOT was done to decrease the allergic reaction by the patients. There was not any record of allergic reactions or side effects after the Phase (1) of the study.

The measurements and statistical data are as below:

Table (1) shows the number of patients, gender and the range of their age. As we can see, the highest number cancer types belong to the breast cancer and the lowest belongs to the kidney, colorectal, and lung cancer.

Table 1

Number	Cancer Types	Number of Patients	Male	Female	Range of Age
1	Brain Cancer	11	7	4	35–75
2	Breast Cancer	18	0	18	25–75
3	Colorectal Cancer	5	1	4	42–67
4	Kidney Cancer	5	3	2	25–60
5	Liver Cancer	10	8	2	35–64
6	Lung Cancer	5	4	1	40–70

As we can observe in the Table (2), the saliva pH of the cancer patients has improved by the SKD and IOT.

Table (3) and Figure (1) shows that the tumor size average of the cancer patients is decreased by 58% after 90 days of the controlled trial.

Table 2

Cancer Types	Saliva pH Range Before Treatment	Saliva pH Range After Phase (1) of the Treatment
Brain Cancer	6.5–6.9	7.0–7.6
Breast Cancer	6.8–7.1	7.0–7.3
Colorectal Cancer	6.0–6.2	7.0–7.2
Kidney Cancer	6.3–6.5	7.0–7.4
Liver Cancer	6.7–6.9	7.1–7.5
Lung Cancer	6.3–6.7	7.1–7.3

Table 3

Cancer Types	Tumor Size Before Treatment in Millimeter	Tumor Size Average in Millimeter	Tumor Size Average After Phase (1) In Millimeter
Brain Cancer	5.00–29.00	17.00	2.21
Breast Cancer	5.00–30.00	16.50	4.12
Colorectal Cancer	5.00–7.00	6.00	4.50
Kidney Cancer	7.00–9.00	8.00	3.68
Liver Cancer	10.00–26.00	18.00	11.16
Lung Cancer	7.00–22.00	14.50	8.00

Figure 1. Blue line shows the average size of the tumors before the experiment begins and the orange line shows the tumor size of the patients after 90 days.

PHASE (2)

After Phase (1) of this research which took 90 days, 23 of the patients left the experiment due to passing away because of old age, car accident or not having enough hope for the future treatment. Some of them wanted to live with their families or saying goodbye to them and some of them did not do exactly the diet so we decided not to continue the treatment on them. We continued the treatment on the remaining 31 patients for the next 90 days. After Phase (1) of our study, we did not observe any cachexia in the patients.

The Phase (2) of the research is the same as the Phase (1) in the Diet and Intravenous Ozone Therapy (IOT). We decided to enter Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBO2T) and special supplementation including vitamins/minerals and some herbal supplementation in our treatment. There was one session of IOT on Saturdays with 70 ug/cc,

and two sessions HBO2T which took 60 minutes in Mondays and Wednesdays. We did not have any HBO2T chamber so we decided to give the patients the pure oxygen inhalation by the oxygen container for 60 minutes every session.

(Table 4, 5, 6) (Figure 2)

Table 4

Number	Cancer Types	Number of Patients	Male	Female	Range of Age
1	Brain Cancer	7	5	2	35–75
2	Breast Cancer	14	0	14	25–75
3	Colorectal Cancer	1	0	1	45
4	Kidney Cancer	2	1	1	50–62
5	Liver Cancer	5	4	1	35–64
6	Lung Cancer	2	2	0	40–47

Table 5

Cancer Types	Saliva pH Range After Phase (1)	Saliva pH Range After Phase (2)
Brain Cancer	7.0–7.6	7.2–7.5
Breast Cancer	7.0–7.3	7.1–7.3
Colorectal Cancer	7.0–7.2	7.1–7.2
Kidney Cancer	7.0–7.4	7.1–7.5
Liver Cancer	7.1–7.5	7.2–7.4
Lung Cancer	7.1–7.3	7.2–7.3

Table 6

Cancer Types	Tumor Size Average in Millimeter	Tumor Size Average After Phase (1) in Millimeter	Tumor Size Average After Phase (2) in Millimeter
Brain Cancer	17.00	2.21	0.00
Breast Cancer	16.50	4.12	0.00
Colorectal Cancer	6.00	4.50	0.21
Kidney Cancer	8.00	3.68	0.00
Liver Cancer	18.00	11.16	0.00
Lung Cancer	14.50	8.00	0.14

As we can see in Table (5), the saliva pH of the patients is improved from acidic into the alkaline.

Table (6) and Figure (2) show the improvement of the tumor sizes from the beginning of the research, after Phase (1) and after Phase (2). After 180 days of this experiment, we have completely shrunk the tumor in 4 types of cancer patients and the remaining two have had the tumor size profoundly reduced.

Although we tried to find the natural vitamin/mineral supplement, the only one was “Immunace” by “vitabiotics company”, which had the near dosage we wanted to give to the patients. They were given

one tablet of this supplement every night with dinner. They were given 3000 mg of Ascorbic acid (500 mg every two hours), one cup of cottage cheese with 5 gr of flaxseed oil every night for dinner (Table 7).

Figure 2. The blue line shows the tumor size before the experiment begins. The orange line shows the tumor size after Phase (1) of the treatment. The white line shows the shrinkage and improvement of the cancer patients tumors after 180 days.

Table 7. Specific doses for supplements given to the patients.

Daily advantage herbal	Daily dose suggested in SCTP
Chlorella Vulgaris	8000 mg (Early in the morning in the fasting state with water)
Turmeric	500 mg (Three times per day with meal)
L-Taurine	400 mg
Bee Pollen	5000 mg mixed with the low glutamine protein powder
Acetyl-L-Carnitine	2000 mg/day
Green tea extract	500 mg 30 minutes before lunch
Panax Gingeng	100 mg with breakfast
Alpha Lipoic Acid (ALA)	300 mg/Day

Results

This research was a controlled study on 54 cancer patients of several kind of cancers. We have put the study in two phases. Each phase took 90 days with different number of patients. In the Phase (1) there were 54 patients with 6 types of cancer: Brain cancer, Breast cancer, Colorectal Cancer, Kidney Cancer, Liver cancer and Lung cancer. We measured their saliva pH before the therapy in the fasting state which were totally acidic. We began the 5-day water fasting, SKD (with 1200–1500 Cal/Day) and IOT on the patients with no supplementation added. After 90 days we observed the tumor shrinkage obviously in all the patients as we can see in Table 3, and improvement in saliva pH from acidic into alkalinity in 90% of the patients.

In the Phase (2) of the study, the number of patients was reduced to 31 and we introduced supplemental vitamin/minerals, HBO2T and Herbal Supplements. The IOT reduced from two sessions to one session per week and HBO2T to two sessions per week to saturate the cancer cells with more oxygen and increasing the amounts of ROS in cancer cells. After Phase (2) which took another 90 days, the saliva

pH of all patients became alkaline and several tumors disappeared completely: Brain cancer, Breast cancer, Kidney cancer and Liver.

In two types of cancer the tumor did not disappear completely but the tumors shrinkage improved obviously to less than 0.3 mm which was a marvelous result: Colorectal cancer and Lung cancer. The total survival of the patients was 99.7% and the improvement in the saliva pH was 100% in this research which shows the effectiveness of this methodology of cancer treatment.

Discussion

The effective diet introduced in this research is the Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD) programmed by Dr. Somayeh Zaminpira and Dr. Sorush Niknamian. Normal cells use the sophisticated process of respiration to efficiently turn any kind of nutrient that is fat, carbohydrate or protein into high amounts of energy in the form of ATP. This process requires oxygen and breaks food down completely into harmless carbon dioxide and water. Cancer cells use a primitive process of fermentation to inefficiently turn either glucose from carbohydrates or the amino acid glutamine from protein into small quantities of energy in the form of ATP. This process does not require oxygen, and only partially breaks down food molecules into lactic acid and ammonia, which are toxic waste products. The most important result is that fatty acids or more generally, fats cannot be fermented by cells [6]. (Figure 3) shows the basic nutrition contents in the SKD.

Figure 3. The Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD).

The reason behind this kind of diet for cancer patients is to starve cancer cells and make them weak. Most patients cannot use cancer ketogenic diets due to gastrointestinal discomfort or high amount of fat which is 90%. SKD uses 80% fat in the form of saturated animal and coconut oil which are less likely to cause adverse side effects such as diarrhea. Food restriction reduces the incidence of both inherited and acquired cancers in laboratory animals [7]. Most cancer cells grow best when they have access to a combination of glucose and the amino acid glutamine. But, there are some types of cancer cells which do just fine without any glucose as a food source, because they are especially good at burning glutamine. This is why both glucose from dietary carbohydrates and glutamine from dietary protein, need to be

restricted in order to best target cancer cells. Therefore, a low-calorie ketogenic diet consisting of 90% fat, with the rest 10% being made up of protein plus carbohydrate maybe the best way to starve cancer cells. This diet forces normal cells to burn fat for energy. It contains enough protein for normal cells to function properly. Excess protein means excess amino acids and glutamine. The ketogenic diet does

not have to contain any carbohydrate, However, it is not harmful if it contains significant amounts of carbohydrate, as long as calories are kept low. Blood glucose levels respond more to calorie intake than to carbohydrate intake [8]. This is the reason for the lowest glutamine intake in the SKD (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Explanation of different Ketogenic Diets [9].

Ozone has been found to be an extremely safe medical therapy, free from side effects. In a 1980 study done by the German medical society for ozone therapy, 644 therapists were polled regarding their 384,775 patients, comprising a total of 5,979,238 ozone treatments administered. There were only 40 cases of side effects noted out of this number which represents the incredibly low rate of 0.000007% and only 4 fatalities. Ozone has thus proven to be the safest medical therapy ever devised [10]. Ozone therapy causes an increase in the red blood cell glycolysis rate. This leads to the stimulation of 2,3-diphosphoglycerate which leads to an increase in the amount of oxygen released to the tissues. Ozone activates the Krebs cycle by enhancing oxidative carboxylation of pyruvate, stimulating production of ATP. It also causes a significant reduction in NADH and helps to oxidize cytochrome C. There is a stimulation of production of enzymes which act as free radical scavengers and cell-wall protectors: glutathione peroxidase, catalase and superoxide dismutase. Production of prostacyline, a vasodilator, is also induced by O₃ [11].

Ozone administered at a concentration of between 30 and 55 µg/cc causes the greatest increase in the production of interferon and the greatest output of tumor necrosis factor and interleukin-2. The production of interleukin-2 launches an entire cascade of subsequent immunological reactions. [11] Ozone exposure induces a significant mean decrement in vital capacity. It significantly increases mean airway resistance and specific airway resistance but does not change dynamic or static pulmonary compliance or viscous or elastic work. It also significantly reduces maximal transpulmonary pressure. And further more significantly increases respiratory rate and decreases tidal volume [12–20].

There were no side effects like allergic reactions and gastrointestinal discomfort of this methodology of treatment recorded in this research and it was safe. HBO2T in combination with IOT and SKD reduced the acidity and pain in the patients as well.

We name this methodology used in this treatment the Sorush Cancer Treatment Protocol (SCTP). This protocol includes: 5-day water fasting, SKD, IOT, HBO2T, natural Vitamin/Mineral Supplements, Herbal Supplements, 3000–5000 mg ascorbic acid, probiotic foods and cottage cheese mixed with flaxseed oil. The total calorie intake by the patients should be 1200–1500 Cal/Day. The dietary restrictions in this protocol are: Dairy, Industrial Vegetable oils, Margarines, Alcohol, Gluten, Soy Products (Miso and Natto are exceptional), Artificial Sweeteners as well as Stevia, Fruit juices and any types of sugar including Honey. The duration of the SCTP should not exceed 6 months to reduce the possibilities of ketoacidosis occurrence in patients.

Acknowledgement

This research is sponsored by the Violet Cancer Institute (VCI) and Weston A. Price Foundation (WAPF).

Conclusion

Using the Specific Ketogenic Diet (SKD) in combination with the Intravenous Ozone Therapy (IOT) resulted in the shrinkage in 6 cancer tumor types (Brain Cancer, Breast Cancer, Colorectal Cancer, Kidney Cancer, Liver Cancer and Lung Cancer) in vivo and improved the fasted saliva pH of the patients from acidic into alkaline after 90 days. By introducing the supplements including Vitamin/Mineral,

Herbal supplements shown in (Table 7), Ascorbic Acid mega dosage (3000 mg/day) and Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBO2T) into our research, all the patients went into complete remission except colorectal and lung cancer in 180 days. The tumors of the remaining cancer patients decreased to less than 0.3 mm in size which shows the effectiveness of this cancer treatment protocol. There were no records of side effects including gastrointestinal discomfort and cachexia in this experiment. The pain related to the type of tumors in patients improved, the saliva pH of all patients became alkaline and the lifestyle of all patients improved after 180 day of the treatment. that the diet needs to be organic and that foods of the highest quality should be chosen. We suggest not using the SKD for more than 6 months to reduce the possibility of ketoacidosis in patients (Figure 5).

Figure 5. SCTP procedure in brief.

List of Abbreviations:

EMHC: Evolutionary Metabolic Hypothesis of Cancer

SKD: Specific Ketogenic Diet

IOT: Intravenous Ozone Therapy

ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species

HBO2T: Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy

SCTP: Sorush Cancer Treatment Protocol

References

1. The Evolution of Electron-Transport Chains, Molecular Biology of the Cell. 4th edition. 2002, Bruce Alberts, Alexander Johnson, Julian Lewis, Martin Raff, Keith Roberts, and Peter Walter; Copyright © 1983, 1989, 1994, Bruce Alberts, Dennis Bray, Julian Lewis, Martin Raff, Keith Roberts, and James D. Watson. Bookshelf ID: NBK26849.
2. Keeling PJ, Archibald JM (2008) Organelle evolution: what's in a name? *Curr Biol* 18: 345–347. [crossref]
3. WARBURG O (1956) On the origin of cancer cells. *Science* 123: 309–314. [crossref]

4. Volek JS, Fernandez ML, Feinman RD, Phinney SD (2008) Dietary carbohydrate restriction induces a unique metabolic state positively affecting atherogenic dyslipidemia, fatty acid partitioning, and metabolic syndrome. *Prog Lipid Res* 47: 307–318. [crossref]
5. Allen BG, Bhatia SK, Anderson CM, EichenbergerGilmore JM, Sibenaller ZA, et al. (2014) Ketogenic diets as an adjuvant cancer therapy: History and potential mechanism. *Redox Biol* 2: 963–970.
6. Sorush Niknamian (2016) The Prime Cause, Prevention and Treatment of Cancer, International Science and Investigation Journal, ISSN: 2251–8576, 5(5), Journal homepage: www.isijournal.info.
7. Valter D Longo, Luigi Fontana (2010) Calorie restriction and cancer prevention: metabolic and molecular mechanisms, Trends Pharmacol Sci. Author manuscript; available in PMC 2011 Feb 1. Published in final edited form as: *Trends Pharmacol Sci* 31: 89–98.
8. Chevrollier A, Loiseau D, Gautier F, Malthiery Y, Stepien G (2005) ANT2 expression under hypoxic conditions produces opposite cell-cycle behavior in 143B and HepG2 cancer cells. *Mol Carcinog* 42: 1–8. [crossref]
9. Allen BG, Bhatia SK, Anderson CM, EichenbergerGilmore JM, Sibenaller ZA, et al. (2014) Ketogenic diets as an adjuvant cancer therapy: History and potential mechanism. *Redox Biol* 2: 963–970.
10. Somayah Zaminpira, Sorush Niknamian, LAP LAMBERT PUBLICATION GROUP, 2017, [ISBN: 978-620-2-05082-1]
11. Washutti J, Viebahn R, Steiner I (1990) The influence of ozone on tumor tissue in comparison with healthy tissue. *Ozone Sci Engg* 12: 65–72.
12. Washutti J, Viebahn R, Steiner I (1989) Immunological examinations in patients with chronic conditions under administration of ozone/oxygen mixtures. *Ozone Sci Engg* 11: 411–417.
13. Zänker KS, Kroczeck R (1990) In vitro synergistic activity of 5-fluorouracil with low-dose ozone against a chemoresistant tumor cell line and fresh human tumor cells. *Int J Exp Clin Chemother* 36: 147–154.
14. Bocci V, Paulesu L (1990) Studies on the biological effects of ozone 1. Induction of interferon gamma on human leucocytes. *Haematologica* 75: 510–515. [crossref]
15. Viebahn-Hansler R (1991) Ozone therapy-the underlying therapeutical concept and models of efficacy. *Erfahrungs Heilkunde* 4: 40.
16. Kawalski H1, Sondej J, CierpioÅ.,-Tracz E (1992) The use of ozonotherapy in the nose correction operations. *Acta Chir Plast* 34: 182–184. [crossref]
17. Johnson AS, Ferrara JJ, Steinberg SM (1993) Irrigation of the abdominal cavity in the treatment of experimentally induced microbial peritonitis: efficacy of ozonated saline. *Am Surg J* 59: 297–303.
18. Gérard V, Sunnen MD (2003) SARS and ozone therapy: Theoretical considerations.
19. Why consider ozone therapy/oxygen Spa as alternative treatment dallas Fort Worth? [cited in 2010].
20. Viebahn-Hänsler R (2003) The use of ozone in medicine: Mechanisms of action. Munich. 2003. May 23–25.

Citation:

Somayah Zaminpira, Sorush Niknamian, Stephanie Seneff, Dominic D'Agostino (2019) The Positive Effect of Skd Plus Iot and Hbo2t In The Treatment Of Cancer [Introducing Sorush Cancer Treatment Protocol (Sctp)]. *Cancer Stud Ther J* Volume 4(1):1–6.